

Project¹ Number: 101022502
Project Acronym: MWER

Project title: The Machine as a Code of the New Political and Social Order in the Artistic Avant-gardes in Western Europe and Russia after the First World War

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

¹ The term 'project' used in this template equates to an 'action' in certain other Horizon 2020 documentation

Abstract

The project <MWER> will contribute to our understanding of and engagement with Europe's cultural diversity and its past. Its goal is to study the interconnections and circulation between different artistic avant-gardes in Europe, especially in Western Europe and Russia, after the First World War and the Revolution, with an emphasis on the history of social and political discourse and ideas. It focuses on the pivotal topic of the machine, which connects the avant-gardes usually considered as separate entities throughout this period. It is not only the modernistic tendency, which characterises almost all references to the machine in Western Europe and Russia, that is of interest. Of even greater importance are the hitherto insufficiently investigated connections between artistic theory and practice, on the one hand, and the visions of political and social reorganisation after the First World War and the Russian Revolution which result from these references to the machine, on the other hand. The idea of the machine became a powerful discursive focus of the transition from an individualistic to a collectivistic vision of man and his social order and organisation in both the western and Russian avant-gardes. Nevertheless, it is significant to stress the persistence of national languages both in the arts as such and in the particular case of the discourse on the machine. Further, we are dealing here with modernism, a field of utopian political and artistic avant-gardes which aim at founding a 'new world'. MWER also has a contemporary impact. It serves as an impetus to reflect on the 'big machine' of the present, which is produced by digitalization and the internet: big data and social media, automatization and artificial intelligence. The machine experienced a paradigmatic transformation in the twenties, which also describes the "archaeology" of the deep transformation which confronts our societies today. Additionally, MWER investigates western European and Soviet urbanism and relates these two cultures to each other. The goal of the former was to correct the evil of the city, while the latter aimed to construct a new society. In this way, MWER stimulates present-day reflection on cities in a globalised world. The circulation of Taylorism and Fordism between North America, Western Europe and Russia through the discourse about machines is, as an example of global knowledge exchange, also of great relevance for today's globalised world.

The project has four broad research objectives, which are closely entangled with each other. Each is achievable in its own right, but their interrelation enhances the historiographical significance of the project. The objectives are as follows:

1. To analyse, for the first time, the pivotal role the discourses on the machine played for the interactions and entanglements of the avant-gardes.
2. To investigate the insufficiently studied connections between artistic theory and practice, on the one hand, and the visions of political and social reorganization after the First World War and Revolution, which resulted from references to the machine, on the other.
3. To systematically reveal, for the first time, the circulation of protagonists, ideas and initiatives between the artistic avant-gardes of Western Europe and Russia after the First World War and the Revolution.
4. To analyze the extent to which (social) sciences, such as Alexander Bogdanov's systems theory, scientific management (Taylorism) and social, economic and management theory (Fordism), affected the artistic avant-gardes and, through them, entire societies.

Interdisciplinarity is of fundamental importance for the project. My approach will focus on a descriptive methodological foam. The project will focus on the entanglements between Western and Russian avant-gardes, concerning the pivotal topic of the machine. My research will also be supported by archival sources.

I am studying the new bibliography of the Russian avant-garde. At the same time, I am looking at contemporary magazines - Russian, English, French, and Italian - which were important points of contact for the international avant-gardes. Furthermore, I am looking at Archive materials at

MOMA, founded in 1929 by Alfred Barr. He had a lifelong interest in the art and culture of Russia. A vast spectrum of Russian contemporary published material is at the New York Public Library. I am using libraries and archives in New York City and also using digital collections. I will work in the Italian Archive Enrico Prampolini, Rome, but I have not yet decided whether I will also work in other European archives. In short, I am intersecting Western and Russian artist theories with the economic and social situation in the USSR and the Western world after the Great War and the October Revolution.

1. Data Summary

	Data Type	Data Source	URL of collection (if available)	Access and Reuse Conditions	Data Format (file types)	Estimated Size	Notes
Reused Data	Physical Collection, Paper: Department of Public Information / Communications Records; Abby Aldrich Rockefeller Albums; Alfred H. Barr, Jr. Papers; Vladimir Isdebsky Papers	MOMA Archive	https://www.moma.org/research-and-learning/archives/finding-aids	I registered as a user to access the collection material. The data are allowed to use only for personal use. I can make photos and cite sources, but I can't reproduce them. Some Exhibition catalogues of the 1920s and 1930s are online, and everybody can access them.	Paper; microfiches; JPEG		
	Secondary Literature	NYU Library	https://library.nyu.edu/about/collections/search-collections/	As Faculty Member at NYU I can access many books on line, but I cannot share them. I also use physical books.	doc/rtf/txt		
	Physical collection, Books; Magazines: <i>Строительство Москвы</i> ; <i>Строительная Промышленность</i> ; <i>Weekly News Bulletin</i>	NYPL	https://www.nypl.org/research/research-catalog/bib/b14163382	I registered as a user to access the collection material. The data are allowed to use only for personal use. The magazine <i>Строительство Москвы</i> is online	Paper		

	Physical Collection, Paper: Dada '291'-1924; Noah Goldowsky.	Solomon R. Guggenheim Museum	https://www.guggenheim.org/library-archives	I registered as a user to access the collection material. The data are allowed to use only for personal use. I can make photos for personal use and cite sources, but I can't reproduce them.	Paper		
	Physical Collection, Paper: Department of Public Information / Communications Records; Abby Aldrich Rockefeller Albums; Alfred H. Barr, Jr. Papers; Vladimir Isdebsky Papers	MOMA Archive	https://www.moma.org/research-and-learning/archives/finding-aids	I registered as a user to access the collection material. The data are allowed to use only for personal use. I can make photos and cite sources, but I can't reproduce them. Some Exhibition catalogues of the 1920s and 1930s are online, and everybody can access them.	JPEG; Mfs.		
	Physical collection, Books; Magazine.	NYPL	https://www.nypl.org/research/research-catalog/bib/b14163382	I registered as a user to access the collection material. The data are allowed to use only for personal use. I can make photos and cite sources, but I can't reproduce them. The magazine <i>Строительство</i>	PDF		

				<i>Москвы</i> is online, free accessible.			
Physical Collection, Paper: Department of Public Information / Communications Records; Abby Aldrich Rockefeller Albums; Alfred H. Barr, Jr. Papers;	MOMA Archive	https://www.moma.org/research-and-learning/archives/finding-aids	I registered as a user to access the collection. The data are allowed to use only for personal use.	PDF			
Physical Collection, Paper	Solomon R. Guggenheim Museum	https://www.guggenheim.org/library-archives	I registered as a user to access the collection material. The data are allowed to use only for personal use. I can make photos and cite sources, but I can't reproduce them.	PDF			

Generated Data	Physical Collection, Paper: Department of Public Information / Communications Records; Abby Aldrich Rockefeller Albums; Alfred H. Barr, Jr. Papers; Vladimir Isdebsky Papers	MOMA Archive	https://www.moma.org/research-and-learning/archives/finding-aids	I registered as a user to access the collection material. The data are allowed to use only for personal use. I can make photos and cite sources, but I can't reproduce them. Some Exhibition catalogues of the 1920s and 1930s are online, and everybody can access them.	JPEG; Mfs.		
	Physical collection, Books; Magazine.	NYPL	https://www.nypl.org/research/research-catalog/bib/b14163382	I registered as a user to access the collection material. The data are allowed to use only for personal use. I can make photos and cite sources, but I can't reproduce them. The magazine <i>Строительство Москвы</i> is online, free accessible.	PDF		

	Physical Collection, Paper: Department of Public Information / Communications Records; Abby Aldrich Rockefeller Albums; Alfred H. Barr, Jr. Papers;	MOMA Archive	https://www.moma.org/research-and-learning/archives/finding-aids	I registered as a user to access the collection. The data are allowed to use only for personal use.	PDF		
	Physical Collection, Paper	Solomon R. Guggenheim Museum	https://www.guggenheim.org/library-archives	I registered as a user to access the collection material. The data are allowed to use only for personal use. I can make photos and cite sources, but I can't reproduce them.	PDF		

To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Primarily to other researchers working on similar issues (artistic avant-gardes, history of social and political discourse and ideas, the concept of the machine in the 1920s)

2. FAIR data

2. 1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?

I will use Zotero to manage the data (secondary literature and primary sources) during the project. The data that I will make discoverable is the full project bibliography. I will share it via a repository -- <https://hcommons.org/core/>

What naming conventions do you follow?

I adopt the same file naming approach for all published works (books, articles, magazines), whether historical primary or secondary sources. For secondary literature, I will use AuthorsDate.pdf (CamelCase).. For primary sources, I will use the name of the collections, like MOMA, Paper Alfred Barr. also use a file folder structure named URSS to separate primary sources from secondary sources.

Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

I will use the following Keywords: Machine, Russian avant-garde in the 1920s, Western avant-garde, Taylorism, Fordism.

Do you provide clear version numbers?

I add the date to the front to differentiate between various versions of the file.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions.

I make my bibliography available. In addition, some of the data that I reuse are openly available, as indicated in the data summary table on pp. 7-11.

How will the data be made accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?

The bibliography will be made accessible through Hcommons. Google, Google Scholar, SHARE, Altmetric, and BASE-OA index hcommons CORE.

Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? Preference should be given to certified repositories which support open access where possible.

The data and associated metadata will be accessible on Hcommons.

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?

Yes, I have discussed arrangements with the personnel responsible for data management at Scuola Normale Superiore.

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?

There are no restrictions on access.

Is there a need for a data access committee?

No.

Are there well described conditions for access (i.e. a machine readable license)?

HCommons Core permits to assign Creative Commons licenses to items deposited in the repository. I will assign the CC-BY license to items I deposit in HCommons (i.e. the bibliography). There will be no further conditions applied for accessing items deposited in HCommons Core; the identity of persons accessing the data in HCommons is not ascertained. I will use CC-BY license.

2.3. Making data interoperable

Are the data produced in the project interoperable, that is allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. (i.e. adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins)?

Data will be made available as an export file from Zotero. Zotero supports various data export formats (e.g. RIS, RDF, BibTeX). Data can also be formatted to doc or PDF file. To support interoperability, I will make data available both as a RIS file (standardized interoperable format) and a PDF file (more accessible for end-users to consult).

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable?

I will use the Harvard citation standard to format the bibliographic data I make available.

Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability?

NA

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

NA

2.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

Data produced by the project will be available through a Creative Commons licence (CC BY).

When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

The data will be available as soon as it is ready; there will be no specific dates of release as the release will depend on the development of the project. But all the relevant data will be available for re-use before the project's end date (31 August 2025). Data will not be embargoed.

Are the data produced and/or used in the project usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.

Data re-used and generated in this project is accessible and re-usable under specific conditions (see the data summary table on p. X). The project will make available for re-use by third party the full bibliography of the project.

How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

The data will be permanently reusable.

Are data quality assurance processes described?

3. Allocation of resources

What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project?

The costs are related to personal time. I understand that the cost is labour time, but I think it is really hard to give a number to this labor time because it is so integrated with my research activities in this one-person project.

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to open access to research data are eligible as part of the Horizon 2020 grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).

The cost is covered from my grant (e.g. research and training unit cost).

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

I, as the Project Coordinator.

Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?

The bibliography will be available under HCommons.

4. Data security

What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)?

The data will be backed up daily on my Hardware disk in a folder named URSS. It is divided in primary sources and secondary Literature. The data is located in my password-protected computer.

Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?

The data I reuse are already preserved in archives, museums and other cultural heritage organizations (see the data summary). Some of the data I generate are allowed to use only for personal use. The data I am able to deposit in repositories, I will deposit.

5. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

Legal issues relate to the access and re-use conditions of the data I re-use (see the data summary table here).

Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

I am not collecting personal data.

6. Other issues

Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones?

NA